

agenda process
green hydrogen

Position Paper

Production

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Content

1. Definition of scope for Green Hydrogen Production	4
1.1 Description of status quo	4
1.2 Target setting of the Agenda Process	6
1.3 Needs assessment	7
2. Development of research questions	8
2.1 Production	8
2.2 Electrolysis technologies for green hydrogen production	10
2.3 Gasification and thermochemical processes of biomass and wastes from renewable sources	13
2.4 Photoelectrolysis & photocatalysis (direct solar hydrogen)	14
2.5 Emerging technologies	15
2.6 Overreaching issues	15
2.7 Safety, pre-normative research	16
2.8 Raising public awareness, social acceptance and skills	17
3. Conclusions and main questions	18
Annex	20

1. Definition of scope for Green Hydrogen Production

On 1st December 2020, the Council conclusion of the European Union has invited the Commission and interested Member States to carry out an agenda process for a green hydrogen R&I ERA pilot action in 2021, while ensuring consistency with other related initiatives and without prejudice to the relevance of a broader hydrogen R&I policy approach beyond this ERA pilot action. In this context, green hydrogen production represents, undoubtedly a field in which significant research and innovation efforts are needed.

1.1 Description of status quo

European Strategy for hydrogen production

On 8th July 2020, the European Commission communicated the “Hydrogen strategy for a climate-neutral Europe” to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and social committee and the committee of the Regions. The strategic document presented by the European Commission focuses on the production and use of green hydrogen. The EU strategy indicates, as priority, the installation of electrolyzers in Europe between 2020 and 2024 with a capacity of up to 6 GW to produce hydrogen with renewable energy. Producing 1 Mt of green H₂ will facilitate the introduction of the hydrogen vector in several industrial sectors and for sustainable mobility. In this phase, a large increase in local hydrogen clusters and “Hydrogen Valleys” is foreseen. The second phase (2025-2030) foresees 40 GW of electrolyzers and 10 Mt of green hydrogen production to extend its application especially to the steel sector and heavy-duty transport

(by trucks, ships and trains). The third phase concerns a period beyond 2030. The goal for renewable hydrogen is to reach maturity in order to be applied on a large scale. The planned investments until 2030 are of the order of 24-42 billion Euros for electrolyzers, 220-340 billion Euros to connect the production of renewable energy and another 160-200 billion Euros for uses in the application sectors.

Actual EU initiatives related to hydrogen production

The EU research, development and innovation programmes focusing on hydrogen in the past Horizon 2020 framework programme were supported by the Public Private Partnership named **Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking (FCH JU)**. The FCH JU is made up of three partners that is the European Commission, the **Hydrogen Europe** association and the **Hydrogen Europe Research** association. Hydrogen Europe brings together diverse industry and research players, large companies and SMEs, who support the delivery of hydrogen and fuel cells technologies. Hydrogen Europe Research is an association of universities and research & technology organisations that are active in the field of hydrogen and fuel cell. In the new framework programme, Horizon Europe, the **Clean Hydrogen for Europe Partnership** in Cluster 5 Climate, Energy and Mobility will replace the FCH JU. The new partnership aims to accelerate development and deployment of European clean hydrogen technologies, contributing to a sustainable, decarbonised and fully integrated energy system. It will focus on production, distribution and storage of clean hydrogen to supply sectors, which are hard to decarbonise such as heavy industries and heavy-duty transport applications.

The Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the Clean Hydrogen for Europe Partnership respectively the Clean Hydrogen Joint Undertaking forwarded by Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, consists of several strategic objectives and horizontal activities. The three pillars on which the roadmap is structured are (i) production, (ii) storage, transport and distribution and (iii) end usage. The JU's SRIA reports detailed analyses and forecasts for each of the strategic goals, as objectives of the partnership based on what was achieved by FCH-JU.

According to JU's SRIA, in the period 2020-2030, the main sectors of maturity are those related to sustainable mobility, industrial applications in the chemical and steel sectors and applications for the production of heat and electricity in the industry. Applications of electrolyzers for grid balancing, power-to-gas, injection of H₂ into the gas grid (blending with natural gas) and accumulation of surplus renewable energy on a daily and seasonal basis are addressed. Other important fields pertain to the use of fuel cells in combined heat and power (CHP) and Micro CHP systems and the production of hydrogen from the gasification of municipal solid waste (circular hydrogen). From the point of view of the research objectives, in the Horizon Europe framework programme (2021-2027), the priorities regarding hydrogen production have been identified and are essentially the electrolysis and other modes of green hydrogen production; specifically, producing clean hydrogen at low cost and enabling higher integration of renewable within the overall energy system.

Other hydrogen initiatives

At the same time the European hydrogen strategy has been published, the European Commission has established the **European**

Clean Hydrogen Alliance (ECH2A). It aims at an ambitious deployment of hydrogen technologies by 2030, bringing together renewable and low-carbon hydrogen production, demand in industry, mobility and other sectors, and hydrogen transmission and distribution. With the alliance, the EU wants to build its global leadership in this domain, to support the EU's commitment to reach carbon neutrality by 2050. By bringing together industry, science, public authorities and civil society, the alliance will play a crucial role in facilitating the implementation of the European hydrogen strategy vision. It will maximize the impact by engaging all stakeholders in the hydrogen value chain and by mobilising resources to develop an investment agenda to stimulate the roll out of production and use of renewable and low-carbon hydrogen as well as to build a concrete pipeline of projects. This will create the base for a sustainable and competitive industrial hydrogen ecosystem in the EU.

In the framework of the world-wide initiative **Mission Innovation**, the 'Innovation Challenge 8: Renewable and Clean Hydrogen' has the potential to contribute in decarbonising hard to abate sectors, such as industry and heat, which are responsible for two thirds of global emissions and can help unlock the full potential of renewable energy. The goal of this challenge is to increase the cost-competitiveness of clean hydrogen by reducing end-to-end costs to USD 2.00 per kg by 2030. The aim of the Mission is to catalyse cost reductions by increasing research and development in hydrogen technologies and industrial processes and delivering an increase of hydrogen valleys covering production, storage and end-use worldwide by 2030, to unleash a global clean hydrogen economy.

Other initiatives include the **ten-year plan for the development of the European gas infrastructure**. This initiative stresses the importance of the transition and decarbonisation of gas by increasing both production of renewable energy and biomethane obtained from CO₂ (power-to-gas), with hydrogen seen in the long term (2050) as an energy vector.

The **European backbone of the hydrogen distribution network** was prepared by the main European operators of gas transport and storage networks. The document outlines the development strategy proposal for the transport of the new energy vector, which in 2030 will extend for 6800 km, connecting the European hydrogen valleys.

There are other relevant initiatives like the **Hydrogen Council** that aims to promote collaboration on hydrogen among different countries within and outside the EU.

An important topic, which is participating in an invisible way in all strategic documents, concerning hydrogen, is public acceptance. It is a central factor for the accelerated deployment of hydrogen technologies, starting with hydrogen production from renewables. However, those strategic documents cannot reach the public, even the policy makers in many EU countries. The documents have to be adapted for fast public acceptance in a new, more expressive way. For the moment, the most powerful is the voice of journalists. However, more collaborative algorithm is needed, combining actively science, industry and society which is one of the goals of this Agenda process on green hydrogen. It should be noted, that hydrogen is more popular and accepted in the transport sector. This should be used and extended to all economic niches so that we could have real objectives for hydrogen economy deployment.

1.2 Target setting of the Agenda Process

The aim of the agenda process in the field of green hydrogen production is to fill missing parts (gaps) in the other EU initiatives applying a bottom-up approach at EU level with wide participation of the stakeholders through the whole value chain by:

- Joining science, industry and society in the agenda process initiative
- Addressing more in-depth society needs
- Applying a holistic approach for hydrogen production.

With regard to the R&D objectives included in the agenda process, the following definitions are used:

- **Hydrogen production focus is on “Green hydrogen”**, i.e. hydrogen produced from renewable energy sources (RES); thus, all fossil resources are excluded.
- **Short-term objectives:** these refer to the needs of further research, development and demonstration for production technologies which are ready for scaling up and have been already developed at medium-high Technology-Readiness-Level (TRL 6-8, time frame for application 1-3 years)
- **Medium-term objectives:** these refer to further development of technologies and processes that have been validated at laboratory level (TRL 4-6, time frame for application 3-10 years)
- **Long-term objectives:** these refer to breakthrough research (TRL 1-4, time frame for application >10 years)

In all cases, the general aim is that **all these research efforts on short, medium and long-term objectives should be carried out in parallel** to make green hydrogen a wide-scale energy vector at 2030.

Besides focusing on production technologies other relevant aspects of the agenda process are:

- To integrate hydrogen production in the energy system, thus ensuring effective sector coupling, taking advantage of hydrogen being an energy vector
- To Increase the hydrogen role in a circular economy context
- To deploy legislation issues (including regulations, codes and standards - RCS) unified on EU level
- To foster company and technology competition in order to decrease costs of electrolysis (€ net per kW) due to:
 - Increased performance
 - Generated scale effects
- To create hydrogen business cases:
 - OPEX based and CAPEX funded business cases
 - Direct use of electricity for electrolysis (power plant integration): long term projects with low electricity prices --> great potential with photovoltaics
 - Additional electrolysis exemption from net fees (grid cost)
- To increase resilience of energy systems by creating decentralised green hydrogen economies based on 'Hydrogen Hubs' with 10 to 15 MW (and more)

- To promote early stage research to force breakthroughs for overcoming scientific and technological challenges in hydrogen production for the different technologies
- To foster collaboration between research and industry applying both breakthrough and underpinning approaches at low and high TRLs

1.3 Needs assessment

The aim of the agenda process on green hydrogen is to bring the attention, through a public consultation with policy makers, society and other stakeholders, on hydrogen production topics which are not sufficiently addressed by other initiatives or that require, in a holistic context, specific priorities. These are shortly summarised below. It is pointed out that this is not an exhaustive list and will be implemented through the public consultation.

- More fundamental research is required, e.g. research needs at low TRLs to address the present gaps. These regard new technologies based on the use of non-critical raw materials characterised by high performance, efficiency and durability. Breakthrough research is needed to reduce the hydrogen cost to make this energy vector economically competitive at world level.
- Developmental activities, research efforts and strategies to reduce the CAPEX/OPEX of the present technologies; overall objective is to reduce the cost of hydrogen produced per kg
- Demonstration activities to favour the rapid creation of a distributed green hydrogen infrastructure in Europe

- Addressing a common terminology at the EU level (e.g. JRC Report ‘EU harmonised terminology for hydrogen generated by electrolysis’ published - Ares(2021)4778451)
- Addressing a common certification of origin to guarantee sourcing of hydrogen from green sources.
- Promoting programmes addressing traceability, deployment mechanisms and market diffusion for green hydrogen production
- Identifying companies’ demands (bridging industry with science); fostering technology transfer
- Addressing effective exploitation of results from research projects
- Business cases driven R&D (OPEX based business cases; CAPEX will decrease later due to company and technology competition with scale effects and increased performance)
- Joined research and industrial efforts on technological development of recycling of materials and components
- Joined efforts of science, industry and active society for wide public information about the importance of hydrogen production from renewables and its utilisation for fast and efficient global decarbonization

2. Development of research questions

2.1 Production

General presentation (for all topics)

The new agenda process on green hydrogen should operate in synergy with the European

strategy “A hydrogen strategy for a climate-neutral Europe”, the activities relating to the European Green Deal, the activities of the Recovery Plan, the planned activities in Horizon Europe (HE) and, in particular, the partnership of Clean Hydrogen for Europe. The aim of the agenda process is to further promote activities on hydrogen while being complementary to the already existing EU programmes and initiatives. The general approach is to consider the role of the society, the specificities of the EU countries and the different opportunities, taking into account the various existing gaps. Scientific-technological development should promote in particular the creation of synergies, interdisciplinary interactions and an increase in critical mass through the creation of networks of laboratories and research infrastructures with wide access to the EU researchers. The final aim is to enhance the competitiveness of EU industries and research entities, establish synergies among the EU countries, and stimulate initiatives of cooperation between research, industry and policy makers.

Short-term requirements

Short-term requirements should include further development of the technologies that have already reached maturity, further scaling up of processes and plants, e.g. from multi-MW level electrolyser to 100 MW-class electrolysers, while pursuing the following objectives:

- Demonstration of high-power (multi-MW and 100 MW-class) electrolysis technologies that meet cost, performance, duration, dynamics and use of hydrogen in end usage targets (e.g. HRS, P2G, industry etc.)
- Scale up of medium scale highly efficient electrolysers

- Development of production automation and quality control processes
- Demonstration of electrolysis plants directly powered by RES and for grid balancing
- Demonstration of biomass derived hydrogen production processes on a wide scale
- Demonstration of plants for the gasification of waste and biomass for the production of hydrogen and their integration with electrolyser and into production systems
- Demonstration of plants with production of hydrogen from biogas
- Demonstration of a full-size biological reactor for the production of hydrogen from residues
- Development of innovative components to optimise and reduce losses and costs
- Development of tools for monitoring, diagnostics and control of electrolysers
- Development of high-pressure electrolysis stacks to reduce/avoid the subsequent compression phase
- Development of reversible systems (electrolysis/fuel cell) and co-electrolysis (syngas)
- Scale up of the most promising technologies for gasification of biomass and waste including the development of hybrid systems and solar gasification
- Development of photo (electro) chemical systems consisting of large area modules with efficiency >10%; scale up of the most promising technologies to 1-100 kW capacity

Medium-term requirements

In the medium term, further development of industrial products based on already validated technologies and processes is required. In this context, research activities aimed at pursuing diversified objectives are required:

- Increasing efficiency, durability and reliability of the electrolyser stack, photoelectrolysis, modules, biochemical reactors
- Simplification of the BoP to make the hydrogen production systems more economical and more easily interfaced with the electricity grid in the case of electrolysers
- Scaling up of stacks and production systems, development of processing technologies suitable for the realisation of high-power electrolysers
- Integration of solar driven electrochemical hydrogen compression with photovoltaic & electrochemical (PV+EC) and photoelectrochemical systems
- Integration of chemical looping cycles in solar-CSP concentration plants and in traditional power plants or in oxy-combustion processes
- Integration into other production schemes, e.g. (bio)refineries
- Development of advanced in operando monitoring techniques of both processes and relevant catalytic and electronic mechanistic steps to identify avenues to overcome the current performance limitations (conversion efficiency, stability)

- Electrolysers in "co-generation mode" e.g. for exploitation of generated heat, synthetic fuel production, etc.
- Development of innovative solutions for exploitation of the generated O₂
- Demonstration of mid-size plants for the production of hydrogen from direct sunlight.

Long-term requirements

- Significant reduction of costs and increase in efficiency (step-change required)
- Overcome kinetic limitations in hydrogen production reactions
- Develop technologies for high pressure (>150 bar) hydrogen production for >100 kW capacity
- Development and use of new materials, new technologies, new designs and new processes, avoiding critical raw materials
- Study of processes for recycling of components at the end of their life as priority actions to reduce the impact, costs and increase the useful life of all hydrogen production technologies
- Develop optimal dynamic behaviour for the electrolysis systems being this essential for grid balancing service

2.2 Electrolysis technologies for green hydrogen production

Research questions/topics

- Which electrolysis technologies need stronger support in the short, medium and long-term?

The large-scale diffusion of green H₂ is strongly related to decrease of both the cost of electricity and the cost of electrolysis systems while increasing the uptime hours. Moreover, it is important to improve the conversion

efficiency. One of the main requirements is the availability of electrical power from renewable power sources at a competitive cost and in appropriate amounts. In this context, hydrogen can promote the rapid penetration of renewables in the energy system.

Distributed and centralised H₂ production, improvement of the durability and reliability of electrolysers, and reduction of operating and investment costs can ensure the achievement of the European objectives with regard to high purity green hydrogen (5N) production at a cost lower than 2-3 €/kg. This can make green hydrogen competitive with hydrogen from fossil fuels, especially if proper carbon taxes will be applied in EU countries. Regarding the sector coupling, an effective and direct integration of electrochemical systems with renewable energy sources and enhanced interface with the grid are relevant aspects. Hydrogen can provide grid-balancing service, store the surplus of renewable energy, allow seasonal energy storage and can be converted into liquid H₂ vectors (e.g. NH₃) in an integrated way. This can be realised in different geographical areas and at different time-scales. In this regard, it would be important improving the electrolysis technology to make use of waste and sea water.

Current commercial technologies (alkaline, PEM) require to upgrade, upscale, reach a higher manufacturing capacity, and deploy large amounts of (sustainable and affordable) hydrogen for the market to take off. This needs strengthening the value chain. For the necessary cost reduction and efficiency improvement (directly affecting to CAPEX and OPEX figures), new technologies that can drive into that direction are also developed (SOEC, AEM, etc.), and minimisation of critical materials usage is fostered. Production capacity requirement remains quite huge, so

new routes other than water electrolysis, that can offer volume, are to be explored and further developed (biomass, photo, etc.).

With regard to Proton Exchange Membrane (**PEM**) **electrolysis**, it will be necessary for the next years to reduce the content of precious metals (Ir, Ru, Pt) in the catalysts/electrodes and in the long term to develop critical materials-free components including hydrocarbon membranes to replace fluorinated membranes. This gap is presently addressed by another similar but competitive technology, i.e. anion exchange membrane (AEM) electrolysis; however, it is still unclear if AEM electrolysis can reach the same level of performance of PEM electrolysis. Moreover, in the case of AEM electrolysis, it is necessary to develop new/advanced membranes and electrocatalysts. For conventional PEM systems, it will be appropriate in the long term to replace the titanium-based bipolar plates (recently included in the EU 2020 list of critical raw materials) with less expensive and more easily machinable metals or develop innovative coatings maintaining the same corrosion resistance characteristics as well as providing optimal interface resistance.

With regard to **alkaline electrolysis**, although this is a consolidated technology, it will be important to develop a more compact stack design, improve efficiency, achieve high current density with low ohmic losses, facilitate the management of concentrated caustic solutions and improve the purity of the hydrogen produced and the dynamic behaviour of the alkaline electrolysis system in general.

For **solid oxide electrolysers**, it will be necessary in the long term to develop new ceramic electrolytes operating at lower temperatures and nanostructured catalysts. This should include intermediate temperature ceramic proton conducting electrolytes. Other

relevant requirements are the search for efficient and stable systems operating at high pressure, decrease costs through the reduction of critical materials, in particular rare earths, cobalt, etc. It is fundamental to reduce the operating temperatures from the current 750-800°C to 600°C, to improve corrosion resistance, durability and the use of low-cost ferritic steels. It is substantial for the next generation of SOECs to improve the dynamic behaviour and in particular the stability to redox and thermal cycles, to produce compressed hydrogen, to develop reversible cells for polygeneration (high quality fuel, electricity and heat) and for power-to-X-to-power applications and to develop thermal and mass flow management in co-electrolysis systems for syngas production and subsequent conversion. Effective direction is the coupling with chemical/electrochemical reactors for production of ammonia or e-chemicals.

Recycling, re-use and substitution of critical materials are emphasised. There is a need to develop a full end-of-life (EoL) strategy in order to reduce cost through the use of sustainable products and innovation and to alleviate the vulnerabilities in existing supply chains.

For all electrolyser technologies, there is a need on a fundamental scientific level, for research to overcome the slow kinetics of the oxygen evolution half-reaction, which contributes significantly to the limitation of the electricity to hydrogen conversion efficiency.

New electrolysis technologies

Among the other emerging technologies, research efforts for the next years should be addressed to develop **anion exchange polymer membrane electrolysis (AEMEL)** and **proton conduction ceramic electrolysis (PCCEL)**.

Research and development targets for AEM electrolyzers revolve around primary requirements of (a) increasing durability of the MEA, (b) reducing / eliminating the use of PGM and CRM catalysts while maintaining high performance and (c) reducing the concentration of, and possibly eliminating the use of alkaline electrolyte. Point (c) is a techno-economic choice rather than an absolute requirement, and the ability to advance in this direction is tied to advances in (a) and (b). Regarding durability, although the alkaline stability of modern ionomers is excellent when well hydrated, questions remain regarding their susceptibility to free-radical induced degradation mechanisms and also oxidative degradation at the anode side, which operates under high voltage, oxygen concentration, and preferably temperature. With regard to performance and CRM usage, while performance of alkaline membrane and ionomer is not of great concern with added alkaline electrolyte, when reduced concentration or elimination of electrolyte is desired, increasing the alkalinity of the alkaline functional groups becomes a critical need especially for the oxygen side where alkalinity is key to high performance. Finally, the mechanical integrity of alkaline MEA's remains a challenge with respect to durability, as well as to performance especially in low-concentration electrolytes. Since hydrocarbon AEM's and ionomers are not able to be fused by hot-pressing, this is a significant challenge that can be addressed both from the mechano-chemical properties of the ionomer, as well as production/engineering advances.

Proton conducting ceramic electrolysis cells operate at moderate temperatures in the range of 400-600°C, which decreases the degradation problems and ensures cheaper interconnects in respect to solid oxide electrolyzers. This technology generates

instantly pure dry H₂ which avoids the H₂/H₂O separation and ensures conditions for direct compression. An important advantage is the operation in reversible regime and integrability of this technology with other processes. Simultaneous withdrawal of the produced pure H₂ shifts the chemical equilibrium of a number of reactions to the product side, thus intensifying process through enhanced thermodynamics. Hydrogen yield gets increased at milder operation conditions which has a huge impact on PCEC technology integration in processing of energy carriers and green chemicals.

For the sector coupling of electrolyzers, the following relevant aspects should be prioritised:

- Direct coupling of electrolysis with renewables
- Application of electrolyzers in grid balancing services
- Coupling of electrolysis with industrial processes (heat balance etc.)

Flexibility and reactivity to changes in the input conditions and loading effects need to be ascertained. The effects of transient operation on stack and system lifetime are not yet well quantified for large-scale electrolyser systems. Systematic data on the impact of operating parameters on durability is necessary and understanding of degradation mechanisms is crucial under dynamic operation.

In general, a common virtual space for a research database and other information for research groups working in similar topics supporting further collaboration is needed as well as a database for testing facilities.

2.3 Gasification and thermochemical processes of biomass and wastes from renewable sources

Research questions/topics

- Which biomass-based processes need to be considered as suitable for green hydrogen production?

Direct production of hydrogen from intermittent renewable sources, such as wind and solar sources, using electrolysis is characterised by intermittent operation and limited operating times (uptime hours). For large-scale use, the hydrogen supply chain should be integrated with alternative production technologies for continuous use needs, particularly in the industrial field. Thus, the generation of green hydrogen from electrolysis can be complemented by gasification of biomass and/or solid renewable waste. In the long term, conversion of organic waste substances via microorganisms (biotechnologies), catalytic reforming of bio compounds in aqueous phase (APR), gasification in supercritical water (SCWG) are promising.

Thermochemical conversion of biomass such as gasification and pyrogasification are interesting technologies to convert biomass wastes and residues into hydrogen and syngas for fuel application. With regard to gasification of biomass and waste, research needs regard the development of innovative reactors, integrated processes combining syngas production and hydrogen upgrading, materials and processes that improve operational flexibility and conversion efficiency as well as new solutions for the treatment of synthetic gas. The design of catalysts as bed material to avoid TAR and to increase H_2/CO ratio are also challenges of the innovative gasification processes. Significant advantages can rise from

the integration of biomass gasification with the electrolyser due to the possibilities to use the hydrogen to increase carbon conversion and the oxygen stream as oxidant.

New bioreactors with a high production rate for medium and large plants, the development of microbial cells based on innovative processes, configurations, innovative materials and electrodes as well as the development of integrated separation systems are other relevant areas of interest.

With regard to reforming of biomass, biogas and wastes, research is needed on the improvement of reactor design and operating under isothermal conditions for maximising hydrogen production. Main challenges stem from the exothermicity of the process which limits heat transfer. Further on, development of novel catalysts, multifunctional materials and the ability to efficiently operate under isothermal conditions and in membrane reactors are envisaged.

Biogas/biomethane pyrolysis and thermocatalytic cracking with renewable carbon black capture can represent a sustainable energy breakthrough converting dispatchable renewable energy sources into clean energy vectors, including hydrogen, with negative CO_2 emissions. Further, the remaining renewable carbon can start a circular usage as precursor for steel production, cement industry, fuel cell production, batteries, etc. Further research needs are on catalyst regeneration and the reduction/minimisation of clogging of reactor due to carbon black. Metal catalysts are used to drive the process, although cheaper carbon materials can also be used. The technology is at TRL 3-5, and research is needed mostly on adapting the catalysts and the process to the characteristics of biogas (i.e. presence of impurities, hydrocarbons other than methane, etc.). The

development of catalysts with high stability is also key.

The electrooxidation of aqueous solutions of biomass-derived organics (e.g. bioethanol, glycerol, sugars) is an interesting technology that can be used to produce high-purity hydrogen at voltages well below those required for water electrolysis, thereby significantly reducing the energy requirements of the process. Apart from hydrogen, this technology potentially allows the co-production of high-value chemicals in the anode chamber, thereby increasing the economic appeal of the process. This technology is currently at a low TRL 3-4, with improvements required mostly in electrocatalysts used as anodes. Thus, new materials with higher activity and stability while being able to catalyse C-C breaking processes are required before scaling up.

2.4 Photoelectrolysis & photocatalysis (direct solar hydrogen)

Research questions/topics

- Which photo-based technology do you think is most promising?

In the view of long-term applications, the direct conversion of solar energy into hydrogen, by water electrolysis using energy from photons, is an area of growing interest where increasing solar-to-fuel conversion efficiency to values of commercial interest is paramount. In this context, it will be appropriate to develop tandem solar systems and innovative photoelectrolysis or photocatalytic materials and devices, based on non-critical materials. In the next five years, there is an urgent need for standardised benchmarking protocols (similar operating conditions illumination, device temperature, electrolyte/pH, pressure) for photoelectrolysis (photoelectrochemical photoelectrodes, PEC

and photovoltaic integrated electrolysis, PV+EC,) and photocatalysis (PC) to compare the solar to hydrogen conversion efficiency as well as to accurately track progress in device performance. At the same time, there is need to develop new approaches and improve experimental techniques for synthesis, for spectroscopy, for microscopy and modelling of PEC and PC devices to overcome the current limitations of recombination losses, in efficient use of incident photons and limited lifetime in realistic operating conditions. Within the next 10 years, it shall be necessary to scale PEC and PC based technologies from laboratory-scale proof-of-concept systems to demonstrator or pilot level production. This should be accompanied by suitable reactor designs that allow reliable and safe operation for high rates of hydrogen production. In the longer term, there is need to develop the capability to design and prepare highly performing and durable photocatalytic and photoelectrochemical materials on a commercial scale.

As alternatives to tandem approaches for water splitting, approaches based on side-by-side modules with sufficient photovoltage to perform the water splitting reaction are interesting. As any photoelectrochemical system based on PV materials, catalysts, and substrates is expected to have a cost per produced energy unit that is similar to a conventional PV-system plus the extra cost for a catalyst layer and gas handling, tandem approaches could turn out to be too costly. The tandem solar cell market has not yet reached economic competitiveness in comparison to conventional side-by-side PV approaches. The challenges are related to a more expensive device manufacturing from the required spectral matching and cell interconnects, as well as issues related to extra cost to utilize highly concentrated light and thus solar

tracking. These are challenges already acknowledged for tandem devices in PV applications where side-by-side modules instead dominate the market with a lower cost per produced energy unit. Irrespectively of the final application would be based on tandem or side-by-side modules, upscaling and more attention to the rate and stability of the reaction is needed. This is because it is neither the efficiency or the cost of the unit itself that are the key parameters for the final cost of hydrogen, but instead the amount of hydrogen produced during the lifetime of the device, divided by the cost of the device and its maintenance. Therefore, a stable large device with high rate and lower efficiency have the potential to produce cheaper hydrogen than a highly efficient lab-cell with low rate and uncertain stability.

2.5 Emerging technologies

Research questions/topics

- Which emerging technology do you think is most promising?

Electrolysis of sea and waste water is an emerging area of interest especially for developing countries. Pure water is produced from electrochemical hydrogen utilisation.

In this field, it will be also important to promote the development of new systems, research on advanced materials for thermochemical cycles (chemical looping) with high conversion kinetics, fluid-dynamic and thermal optimisation of the redox reactor by direct coupling with solar concentrators and reactor/solar collector integration.

These include concentrated sunlight (CSP) eventually combined with thermodynamic cycles, artificial leaves, water electrolysis through combined and mechanical stresses (ultrasounds) and solar radiation, water

electrolysis through the combination of magnetism and electrocatalysis, biologic processes etc.

- Innovative technologies such as the production of hydrogen through water sono-phono-catalysis (solar energy and mechanical ultrasound stress) have recently emerged and need to address specific attention and research efforts.

2.6 Overreaching issues

Research questions/topics

- Which main overarching topic do you see as more important for green hydrogen production?

Quality of Hydrogen and Hydrogen Guarantees of Origin:

Hydrogen quality guarantees are needed as a product for specific applications (e.g. MetroHyVe European Project for mobility sector). This includes to develop automation and quality control processes for continuous production of large volumes of Hydrogen. Quality control is also important for product manufacturing. Other relevant aspects are quality assurance and standardisation of (performance) tests.

Guarantees of Origin (GOs) can provide transparency on the GHG footprint of the produced hydrogen, the hydrogen production technology, temporal and geographical origin of the hydrogen volumes and other potentially relevant attributes (e.g. European CertifHy project). A necessary step is the development of a single, consistent and reliable set of objectives and of protocols for measurement of the green hydrogen environmental impact based on accepted environmental metrics.

System integration (utility scale production technologies and energy communities for distributed generation via H₂ production):

Hydrogen is at the centre of energy system integration, bridging electricity, gas and fuel infrastructures to make the system more efficient and flexible. Better integration of TEN-E and TEN-T networks, synergies between energy and transport networks can facilitate the flow of Hydrogen from its production point to crucial parts of the European transport and logistics network and make green hydrogen using electrolysis more affordable by reducing investment costs and providing a sustainable business/economical case for the H₂ producers and end-users.

Administrative barriers: For the development of a common hydrogen market, a data base for the legislative framework in every EU country (such as Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Observatory) should be supported and analysed. Based on the results from the analysis a common EU legislative frame should be developed. This approach can be very useful for countries with less experience in hydrogen deployment.

Circular economy: A robust value chain has to be established including the implementation of strong measures to avoid shortages and vulnerability to supply chain bottlenecks for critical parts and components such as catalysts and membranes by discouraging monopolies of supply. Research and innovation is needed for efficient and low-cost recycling of precious metals and other materials within Europe while minimising environmental impacts. Seeds have to be developed for business cases and models based on recycling of electrolysers. New avenues have to be investigated to alleviate possible competition for resources such as PGM (fuel cells), nickel (steel and batteries), iron (steel) and cobalt (batteries).

2.7 Safety, pre-normative research

Research questions/topics

- Which normative and pre-normative barriers need to be overcome for the diffusion of green hydrogen production?

Although considerable progress has been made recently at European and national level on the regulation, all demonstration projects for green hydrogen production have encountered authorisation difficulties which shows that improvements are needed, remaining to be an issue at local, regional and national levels. Joint efforts are necessary to harmonise the regulatory framework for all applications in order not to limit deployment on any region in Europe. This means that specific initiatives should be addressed in this regard involving policy makers, stakeholders, experts and society. Specific programmes should be addressed to the development of safety provisions for hydrogen production and usage, high-pressure storage tanks and towers, for high voltage components of electrolysers and fuel cells, safety for tunnels in the case of trains, airports and ports safety as well as safety problems associated with hydrogen/natural gas mixtures for the gas network, etc.

Standards and regulations: It is necessary to strengthen the standardisation work and to insist on the harmonisation of hydrogen production standards, to support the development of the hydrogen energy industry and give full play to the supporting and leading role of the standard to the industrial development.

2.8 Raising public awareness, social acceptance and skills

Research questions/topics

- What are the main points to consider in order to increase social acceptance?

When scientific results and innovative technologies are introduced into society, their social acceptance depends mainly on their reliability; the introduction of hydrogen is not an exception. Hydrogen has characteristics that are different from existing energy technologies and some historical prejudices associate the technology to the "hydrogen bomb" or even to the "Hindenburg disaster". This makes an extra effort necessary to ensure solid and fail-safe hydrogen technologies and to promote social recognition and acceptance of the technology in order to achieve its widespread use.

Also, the fact that hydrogen has recently raised some kind of "wave", "touching everything" is causing fear to general public. As in the past with biofuels, which were accused of being in conflict with food, electrolysis is now being considered in conflict with the availability of water (even when water consumption is not so relevant). To produce 1 kg of hydrogen, corresponding to a theoretical 39.4 kWh of energy based on the HHV, a minimum of 9 kg of water are required.

Specific concerns of the society also exist regarding the costs of hydrogen. Costs of hydrogen production are expected to decrease in the next years by the effect of new policies, decrease of renewable energy costs, decrease of capital costs and scaling up of production plants. The aim is to achieve 2-3 Euro/kg H₂ target costs by 2030. Moreover, regarding the **Hydrogen Economy Cost**, there are still significant misunderstandings in society's cognition of hydrogen energy systems. New

technology innovations lead to shorter product lifecycles and consumers often face the dilemma of choosing between keeping the existing product and upgrading to a recent version. They deal with stress and uncertainty. Some strategies include refusal, delay and extended decision-making.

The increasing reliance on green hydrogen within the context of a climate-neutral economy raises important geoeconomic questions. While existing dependencies on fossil-fuel imports will decrease over time, climate-friendly industrial production will depend on increasing imports not only of green hydrogen itself, but also of critical resources and inputs for an emerging hydrogen supply chain. A recent report published by the European Commission in the context of the updated New Industrial Strategy identifies hydrogen as an area of particular importance for ensuring the European Union's strategic open autonomy and provides an overview of strategic dependencies and capacities in the hydrogen sector. This should provide a starting point for in-depth research of the geoeconomic implications and trade-offs of different technologies and technological pathways within the field of green hydrogen. This includes analysis and scenario-building exercises to assess existing and future technological and industrial capacities both in Europe and other key economies, potential vulnerabilities as well as geoeconomic and geopolitical impacts. It should also include an assessment of policies, regulations and standards and their impact on Europe's open strategic autonomy in green hydrogen.

Hydrogen production processes and technologies need experts with specific skills but who also have an overall view of hydrogen-related supply chains. Training of dedicated

personnel is essential, especially in the engineering sector, and it is necessary to retrain already trained personnel through technological updating and learning initiatives. A specific moment is the coupling of specialists from renewables and hydrogen production, and the building of new expertise. In addition, it is necessary to train the staff of the authorities in charge of control, safety, maintenance and authorisation as well as enhance school and university education in the field.

Important aspects to be addressed are:

Jobs creation and skills improvement: With fast-changing technologies, people's concern is not finding a new job due to a perceived lack of competencies. People could think they lack the skills to succeed elsewhere in a new hydrogen economy. Even where jobs do disappear, people must have the training to lead to other job opportunities. In this context, it is necessary to establish the basis for educational and training strategies to ensure specialist's skills and knowledge is acquired in a time manner for industry needs in order to provide requalification and define new certified qualifications, roles and related capabilities

In respect to public awareness, new forms of communication for knowledge and information enhancement are needed – more illustrative with higher impact, because consumers will govern the market. In this process hydrogen production, including energy carrier and important raw material for industrial processes, opens new jobs but has to find its place.

Common communication platform of the agenda process (common for production, transport/infrastructure and market stimulation issues and different stakeholder groups)

- Database for research groups/research topics for future partnerships
- Industrial platform for industrial needs
- Civil society space

Educational materials for schools and universities have also been developed as well as training programmes in areas such as safety. These aspects need to be further extended and rolled out in more languages to strengthen the public's access to such material.

3. Conclusions and main questions

A new approach is required for strategic programmes on hydrogen production. It is necessary to create an integrated programme for the hydrogen supply chain with projects that are able to support synergies, collaboration and a critical mass in an interdisciplinary way addressing a wide TRL range (from 1 to 8).

The European hydrogen strategy foresees a huge demand of renewable hydrogen in Europe. Its implementation requires moving towards sustainability, cost effectiveness and capability to deploy. Tools are to be reinforced to foster knowledge translation into products and services and to further develop the value chain.

A common standardisation and regulation framework should be in place, capable to

generate and stand trust as well as to allow the necessary large investments.

Concerns and uncertainties from the society are to be faced. This transition needs to be properly managed.

The new programmes should better focus on overcoming the specific challenges of the hydrogen production sector and the gaps related to hydrogen technologies. Workplans including indicators and specific objectives should be agreed through a broad participation of national bodies and by the systemisation of research activities in the sector. It is necessary to facilitate the creation of joint laboratories between academic organisations and industries while promoting the creation of spin-offs and start-ups. In general, it will be important to create a network of laboratories and to systematise the existing resources in terms of capacity and instrumentation. Facilities should be established in centres that already have a high level of specialisation by promoting broad accessibility on the basis of shared programmes.

The most important advantage of a new European Partnership is its ability to coordinate the otherwise fragmented landscape of stakeholders and to take a concerted approach to research, innovation and deployment, as well as to horizontal and societal aspects, without which the positive impacts will fail to materialise or be severely delayed. The public's acceptance of hydrogen energy needs active popularisation and education, in which the efforts of the government and scientific research institutions are needed. Relevant aspects are evaluation of social acceptance of H₂ technologies at the different levels of the value chain and looking at the different components of community acceptance, market acceptance and socio-

political acceptance. Specific activities and demonstrative events to raise public awareness sufficiently according to the benefits of hydrogen technologies are required. Other aspects deal with the development of educational targets, including service and specific events, e.g. summer and winter schools.

Since hydrogen technologies are emerging on the market, innovative approaches with demonstration accent should be developed for the increase of public awareness and acceptance, for manifestation of the positive social impacts (e.g. new jobs, new skills) and environmental impacts (e.g. carbon emissions reduction, improved quality of air).

Annex

KPIs for electrolyzers technologies

The following key performance indicators (KPI) are taken from two reports published by the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA 2020: GREEN HYDROGEN COST REDUCTION: SCALING UP ELECTROLYSERS TO MEET THE 1.5°C CLIMATE GOAL) and a joint initiative of the European Energy Research Alliance, Joint Research Programme on Fuel Cells and Hydrogen technologies (JP FCH), Hydrogen Europe Research (HER) and the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking (FCH JU) (EERA, JP FCH, HER, FCH JU 2020: KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs) FOR FCH RESEARCH AND INNOVATION, 2020 – 2030).

2020 KPIs

The research and development of materials, thin films, components, cells, stacks, systems peripherals, and integration for water electrolyzers is very much dependent on the definition of a solid and trustworthy state-of-the-art that correctly represents what can currently be found at the commercial level. Only a reliable state-of-the-art allows the implementation of solid baselines to different metrics, such as the physicochemical characteristics of materials, performance, selectivity, durability, cost, and so on. PEM and alkaline electrolyzers have historically relatively well-defined benchmarks, with metrics fairly well known by the R&D community and industry. This is unfortunately not the case for solid oxide and AEM electrolyzers. These are of high potential, but are also much less mature technologies, with only a few companies and OEMs interested or involved in their manufacture and commercialisation.

Alkaline electrolyzers

Concerning stacks for alkaline electrolyzers, the key areas to focus on are the electrodes and the diaphragms. Bipolar plates and PTLs have less priority, since they are based on stainless steel plates coated with nickel, which are already significant, cost-effective components. Strategies to integrate PTLs into electrodes and consequently diaphragms can also be of key importance in reducing costs, as outlined below:

Increase current densities: The current densities of the stacks can be increased, from the current, 0.5 A/cm² to more advanced units of 2-3 A/cm². This current density increase cannot be made, however, at the penalty of lower efficiency.

Higher current densities have already been accomplished by some manufacturers, too, with electrode-separator packages that can deliver a performance range as high as 1.2 A/cm² at 2 volts (V) now available. Power densities of 2-3 W/cm² could be achieved by demonstrating thinner diaphragms or membranes for alkaline electrolyzers. As with PEM, alkaline electrolyzers also need to improve their voltage efficiency levels, reducing ohmic losses and increasing electrode kinetics.

Reducing diaphragm thickness: This could improve efficiency and reduce electricity consumption. The thinner the diaphragms, the lower the resistance to transporting the OH⁻ species from the cathode to the anode. Eventually, however, this comes at a cost of higher gas permeation, which contributes to

higher safety concerns. The other downside is the lower durability, given the higher chance of pinhole formation in the diaphragm and less mechanical robustness. Overall, the diaphragm thickness should reach values that approach those of PEM and AEM. State-of-the-art membranes for PEM are about 125-175 micrometres (μm) (Babic, 2017) with a potential decrease to 20 μm or lower. Below this point (for PEM), there are limited efficiency benefits. For alkaline electrolyzers, the current diaphragm thickness is about 460 μm . Decreasing this to 50 μm would contribute to improving the efficiency from 53% to 75% at 1 A/cm^2 .

Re-designing catalyst compositions and electrode architectures into electrodes with a high specific surface area: Despite using cheap and widely available Nickel based catalysts for their electrodes, alkaline electrolyzers have traditionally encountered many challenges in moving away from rudimentary, or archaic electrode designs and reaching much higher efficiencies for both hydrogen and oxygen evolution reactions. Efficiency differences with other technologies are small and best-in-class designs result in even higher efficiencies. Table 2 shows a list with the ten main R&D aspects that need to be addressed, so that electrodes used in these stacks can be transformed and implemented in more advanced stack concepts.

Apart from increasing surface area, which was traditionally and simply achieved with Raney-Ni catalysts (nickel-aluminium [Ni-Al], or nickelzinc [Ni-Zn]), the other points are considered moderate and difficult challenges. In addition, any novel concept still needs to keep long-term durability, comparable to those presented by current nickelcoated stainless steel perforated sheets. That is the reason why Raney-Ni electrodes have not been commercially deployed, at least not in large-scale electrodes, since they have presented some critical durability aspects for long-term operation (low mechanical robustness) and much higher costs, due to the use of expensive manufacturing techniques.

Novel PTL concepts: Alkaline electrolyzers are also not well developed in the use of efficient PTLs, potentially based on nickel. This is especially so in regard to optimising these for reduction of mass transport limitations (*e.g.* gas bubble resistance, trapped inside alkaline PTLs), and optimal protective coating alternatives to decrease interface resistances on the anode side.

PEM electrolyzers

Re-designing the stacks can achieve large cost reductions, since it enables the reaching of higher power densities, up from the current (conservative) $2\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ to $6\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ or more in the next few decades. Next, electrodes should be scaled up from the current 1 500-2 000 cm^2 , up to 5 000 cm^2 and eventually 10 000 cm^2 . The larger area should go in tandem with more mechanically robust membranes that can use the same thickness. Such a strategy would allow an increase in the size of the PEM stacks, from the current 1 MW/unit to next generation stacks of 5 MW or even 10 MW per stack. These need to run at much lower levels of cell voltage to allow for an increase in efficiency and the simplification of waste heat management. Reducing membrane thickness: This enables an increase in efficiency, which in turn enables a reduction in electricity consumption. Thick membranes (Nafion N117 with approximately 180 μm thickness, for example) are still state-of-the-art and are responsible for efficiency losses of about 25% (at $2\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$). There are much thinner membranes that are commercially available, with thicknesses as low as 20 μm , yet these are not designed for

electrolysis requirements. This thickness reduction would allow a reduction in efficiency losses to about 6% (at 2A/cm²). Further reduction of membrane thickness, down to 5.0 μm or lower (membraneless electrolysis), is not encouraged, since a decrease of no more than 0.5 kWh/Kg H₂ can be extrapolated. In this case, R&D is therefore not justified. Looking at the experience in PEM fuel cells (reverse process of electrolysis), commercial stacks are already equipped with membranes that are 810 μm thick, as gas permeation is not a concern, since they operate at a much lower pressures (36 bar) on the air side.

The two challenges that arise with thinner membranes are: their lower durability, given their potentially lower mechanical strength and being more prone to defects and pinhole failures; and the manufacturing of such membranes. During manufacturing, the process of enlarging the catalyst coated membranes and porous transport layers into large electrodes is challenging and therefore of high R&D risk. The thin membrane and electrodes need to be mechanically stabilised over the full area to avoid undesired mechanical stresses that can tear these films and delaminate thin electrodes. This is especially critical at differential pressure operations, where one side is subjected to much higher pressures coming from the other electrode.

Re-designing PTLs will be crucial – i.e. with finer structures at the catalyst interface that can better support a thinner membrane and prevent creep failure, thereby enabling lower membrane thickness.

Removing expensive coatings and redesigning the PTLs and bipolar plates: On the anode side, commercial stacks demand the use of platinum coated titanium porous sintered PTLs, which is not possible with non-PGMs at this stage. Platinum loadings on the anodic PTL vary from 1-5 milligrammes per square centimetre (mg/cm²) or 1 2.5 g/kW. Platinum has a dual purpose: to protect the titanium against passivation¹⁷ and provide an optimal interface resistance. This is needed because titanium is prone to severe quick and detrimental passivation. Studies have shown that interface resistance at the PTL is responsible for an electricity consumption as high as 1.35 kWh/Kg H₂ (4% of hydrogen LHV) (Liu et al., 2018; Kang et al., 2020). The bipolar plates made of titanium also possess protective layers of platinum on the anode side, and gold on the cathode. Alternatives are needed for titanium plates, based on such materials as niobium, tantalum and eventually stainless steel approaches, but using protective coatings that are stable and also free from platinum or gold.

Re-designing catalyst-coated membranes: For catalyst coated membranes (electrodes), the strategy can be divided into different timescale scenarios. An initial approach could be to tackle the economies of scale for CCM fabrication via automation over manufacturing, establishing more reliable and less expensive supply-chains for catalysts and membranes, and implementing quality control. If possible, parallel work can be done to reduce the amount of electrocatalysts by re-engineering the electrodes over the membrane. Supply chain for PFSA membranes: For PFSA membranes, various suppliers (e.g. Chemours, Solvay, Asahi-Kasei, 3M and Gore) are available. This is also one of the most solid supply chains for PEM components. Moreover, these membranes have been traditionally supplied at scale for chloroalkali electrolyzers, with membranes reaching areas as high as 3 m². Therefore, significant cost reduction is expected as soon as PEM water electrolyzers reach high market volumes.

AEM electrolyzers

In terms of components, the AEM membrane and ionomer are the main and most challenging. In terms of performance, the most critical item is durability, but also conductivity. Research efforts are targeted to finding AEM membranes with desirable properties (high mechanical, thermal, and chemical stability, ionic conductivity, and lower permeability with respect to electrons and gases). The polymer backbone is responsible for mechanical and thermal stability. The functional group that transports the OH⁻ anion is accountable for the ion exchange capacity, ionic conductivity, and transport number. The trade-off for AEM is between mechanical stability, ionic conductivity and cost. For instance, the production of commercial AEM that achieves a high mechanical stability and high ionic conductivity is challenging and therefore expensive. There are known chemical strategies to increase the AEM ionic conductivity, but it leads to loss of mechanical strength due to excessive water uptake. The AEM then becomes chemically unstable, which leads to poor ionic conductivity. Another major limitation of an AEM is degradation of the polymer due to KOH attack, which quickly reduces the conductivity of the membrane and ionomer within the catalyst layer. The ionic conductivity of an AEM plays a significant role in the performance of the AEM. Higher levels of ion conductivity allow much higher current densities to be achieved. Tasks to increase efficiency and durability of electrodes and PTLs are analogous to those related to alkaline electrolyzers. A progress in this direction has been made by the company Dioxide Materials that produces AEMs for water electrolyzers (e.g. Sustanion X37 type membranes).

Solid Oxide Electrolyzers

The potential for this technology lies in its higher efficiency, while its main challenge is durability. Some of the areas to focus on are: the improvement of electrolyte conductivity, optimisation of chemical and mechanical stability, matching the thermal expansion coefficient to both electrodes, and ensuring minimal reactant crossover. State-of-the-art electrolytes used in these cells have already exhibited remarkable conductivity for stack operation for thousands of hours, but the degradation of the electrolyte (which translates into a reduction in performance) is still of high importance for research. Structural changes within the electrolyte accelerate the formation of voids within its structure, increasing electrolyte resistance. Moreover, electrolyte also reacts with vaporised water and forms volatile products such as nickel hydroxide (Ni(OH)₂) that also deactivates it. As for the other electrolysis technologies, electrodes used for solid oxide stacks are key components, and many key properties are required to provide high efficiency and durability. Table 5 provides a list of challenges and their respective ranking related to future R&D tasks to improve them, both to reach higher efficiency and durability.

Table 1. State-of-the-art and future KPIs for all electrolyser technologies.

	2020	Target 2050	R&D focus
PEM electrolyzers			
Nominal current density	1-2 A/cm ²	4-6 A/cm ²	Design, membrane
Voltage range (limits)	1.4-2.5 V	< 1.7 V	Catalyst, membrane
Operating temperature	50-80°C	80°C	Effect on durability
Cell pressure	< 30 bar	> 70 bar	Membrane, reconversion catalysts
Load range	5%-120%	5%-300%	Membrane
H ₂ purity	99.9%-99.9999%	Same	Membrane
Voltage efficiency (LHV)	50%-68%	>80%	Catalysts
Electrical efficiency (stack)	47-66 kWh/Kg H ₂	< 42 kWh/Kg H ₂	Catalysts/membrane
Electrical efficiency (system)	50-83 kWh/Kg H ₂	< 45 kWh/Kg H ₂	Balance of plant
Lifetime (stack)	50 000-80 000 hours	100 000-120 000 hours	Membrane, catalysts, PTLs
Stack unit size	1 MW	10 MW	MEA, PTL
Electrode area	1 500 cm ²	> 10 000 cm ²	MEA, PTL
Cold start (to nominal load)	< 20 minutes	< 5 minutes	Insulation (design)
Capital costs (stack) minimum 1 MW	USD 400/kW	< USD 100/kW	MEA, PTLs, BPs
Capital Costs (system) minimum 10 MW	700-1400 USD/kW	< 200 USD/kW	Rectifier, water purification
Alkaline electrolyzers			
Nominal current density	0.2-0.8 A/cm ²	> 2 A/cm ²	Diaphragm
Voltage range (limits)	1.4-3 V	< 1.7 V	Catalysts
Operating temperature	70-90°C	> 90°C	Diaphragm, frames, balance of plant components
Cell pressure	< 30 bar	> 70 bar	Diaphragm, cell, frames
Load range	15%-100%	5%-300%	Diaphragm
H ₂ purity	99.9%-99.9998%	> 99.9999%	Diaphragm
Voltage efficiency (LHV)	50%-68%	> 70%	Catalysts, temperature

Electrical efficiency (stack)	47-66 kWh/Kg H ₂	< 42 kWh/Kg H ₂	Diaphragm, catalysts
Electrical efficiency (system)	50-78 kWh/Kg H ₂	< 45 kWh/Kg H ₂	Balance of plant
Lifetime (stack)	60 000 hours	100 000 hours	Electrodes
Stack unit size	1 MW	10 MW	Electrodes
Electrode area	10 000-30 000 cm ²	30 000 cm ²	Electrodes
Cold start (to nominal load)	< 50 minutes	< 30 minutes	Insulation (design)
Capital costs (stack) minimum 1 MW	USD 270/kW	< USD 100/kW	Electrodes
Capital costs (system) minimum 10 MW	USD 500-1 000/kW	< USD 200/kW	Balance of plant
AEM electrolyzers			
Nominal current density	0.2-2 A/cm ²	> 2 A/cm ²	Membrane, reconversion catalysts
Voltage range (limits)	1.4-2.0 V	< 2 V	Catalyst
Operating temperature	40-60°C	80°C	Effect on durability
Cell pressure	< 35 bar	> 70 bar	Membrane
Load range	5%-100%	5%-200%	Membrane
H ₂ purity	99.9%-99.999%	> 99.9999%	Membrane
Voltage efficiency (LHV)	52%-67%	> 75%	Catalysts
Electrical efficiency (stack)	51.5-66 kWh/Kg H ₂	< 42 kWh/Kg H ₂	Catalysts/membrane
Electrical efficiency (system)	57-69 kWh/Kg H ₂	< 45 kWh/Kg H ₂	Balance of plant
Lifetime (stack)	> 5 000 hours	100 000 hours	Membrane, electrodes
Stack unit size	2.5 kW	2 MW	MEA
Electrode area	< 300 cm ²	1 000 cm ²	MEA
Cold start (to nominal load)	< 20 minutes	< 5 minutes	Insulation (design)
Capital costs (stack) minimum 1 MW	Unknown	< USD 100/kW	MEA
Capital costs (system) minimum 10 MW	Unknown	< USD 200/kW	Rectifier
Solid oxide electrolyzers			
Nominal current density	0.3-1 A/cm ²	> 2 A/cm ²	Electrolyte, electrodes

Voltage range (limits)	1.0-1.5 V	< 1.48 V	Catalysts
Operating temperature	700-850°C	< 600°C	Electrolyte
Cell pressure	1 bar	> 20 bar	Electrolyte, electrodes
Load range	30%-125%	0%-200%	Electrolyte, electrodes
H ₂ purity	99.9%	> 99.9999%	Electrolyte, electrodes
Voltage efficiency (LHV)	75%-85 %	> 85%	Catalysts
Electrical efficiency (stack)	35-50 kWh/Kg H ₂	< 35 kWh/Kg H ₂	Electrolyte, electrodes
Electrical efficiency (system)	40-50 kWh/Kg H ₂	< 40 kWh/Kg H ₂	Balance of plant
Lifetime (stack)	< 20 000 hours	80 000 hours	All
Stack unit size	5 kW	200 kW	All
Electrode area	200 cm ²	500 cm ²	All
Cold start (to nominal load)	> 600 minutes	< 300 minutes	Insulation (design)
Capital costs (stack) minimum 1 MW	> USD 2 000/kW	< USD 200/kW	Electrolyte, electrodes
Capital costs (system) minimum 1 MW	Unknown	< USD 300/kW	All

EERA Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for FCH research and innovation, 2020 – 2030

The Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking (FCH JU) has defined application-level KPIs in their latest version of the Multi-Annual Work Programme (MAWP): these are presented below for high-level referencing. Concentrating on translating these high-level KPIs to intermediate technical milestones for research and development, the R&D KPIs are conceived horizontally across applications, focusing on specific scientific topics. The ultimate link to, and impact on, application-specific KPIs – i.e. those that are most important from the end-user perspective – is in any case explicitly provided for each R&D-specific KPI. The appendix form of these R&D KPIs will allow to update the values more easily as technology progresses. In this Annex I of the Seed Paper we provide only KPIs for various electrolyser technologies.

Application-specific KPIs established in the FCH JU MAWP (2014-2020)

Table 2. State-of-the-art and future targets for hydrogen production from renewable electricity for energy storage and grid balancing using **alkaline electrolysers**.

No	Parameter	Unit	State of the art		FCH-JU target		
			2012	2017	2020	2024	2030
Generic system*							
1	Electricity consumption @nominal capacity	kWh/kg	57	51	50	49	48
2	Capital cost	€/(kg/d) (€/kW)	8,000 (~3000)	1,600 (750)	1,250 (600)	1,000 (480)	800 (400)
3	O&M cost	€/(kg/d)/yr	160	32	26	20	16
Stack							
4	Degradation	%/1000hrs	-	0,13	0,12	0,11	0,10
5	Current density	A/cm ²	0,3	0,5	0,7	0,7	0,8
6	Use of critical raw materials as catalysts	mg/W	-	7,3	3,4	2,1	0,7

Notes:

*Standard boundary conditions that apply to all system KPIs: input of 6kV AC power and tap water; output of hydrogen meeting ISO 14687-2 at a pressure of 30 bar. Correction factors may be applied if actual boundary conditions are different.

- 2) Capital cost are based on 100MW production volume for a single company and on a 10-year system lifetime running in steady state operation, whereby end of life is defined as 10% increase in energy required for production of hydrogen. Stack replacements are not included in capital cost. Cost are for installation on a pre-prepared site (fundament/building and necessary connections are available). Transformers and rectifiers are to be included in the capital cost;
- 3) Operation and maintenance cost averaged over the first 10 years of the system. Potential stack replacements are included in O&M cost. Electricity costs are not included in O&M cost;
- 4) Stack degradation defined as percentage efficiency loss when run at nominal capacity. For example, 0.125%/1000h results in 10% increase in energy consumption over a 10-year lifespan with 8000 operating hours per year;
- 5) The critical raw material considered here is Cobalt. Other materials can be used as the anode or cathode catalysts for alkaline electrolysers. 7,3 mg/W derives from a cell potential of 1,7 V and a current density of 0,5 A/cm², equivalent to 6,2 mg/cm².

Table 3. State-of-the-art and future targets for hydrogen production from renewable electricity for energy storage and grid balancing using **PEM electrolyzers**

No	Parameter	Unit	State of the art		FCH-JU target		
			2012	2017	2020	2024	2030
Generic system							
1	Electricity consumption @nominal capacity	kWh/kg	60	58	55	52	50
2	Capital cost	€/(kg/d) (€/kW)	8000 (~3000)	2900 (1200)	2000 (900)	1500 (700)	1000 (500)
3	O&M cost	€/(kg/d)/yr	160	58	41	30	21
Specific system							
4	Hot idle ramp time	sec	60	10	2	1	1
5	Cold start ramp time	sec	300	120	30	10	10
6	Footprint	m ² /MW	-	120	100	80	45
Stack							
7	Degradation	%/1000hrs	0,375	0,250	0,190	0,125	0,12
8	Current density PEM	A/cm ²	1,7	2,0	2,2	2,4	2,5
9	Use of critical raw materials as catalysts	mg/W	-	5,0	2,7	1,25	0,4

Notes:

- 1) to 3) and 7) similar conditions as for alkaline technology (previous table);
- 4) The time from hot idle to nominal power production, whereby hot idle means readiness of the system for immediate ramp-up. Power consumption at hot idle as percentage of nominal power, measured at 15°C outside temperature;
- 5) The time from cold start from -20°C to nominal power;
- 9) This is mainly including ruthenium and iridium as the anode catalyst and platinum as the cathode catalyst (2,0 mg/cm² at the anode and 0,5 mg/cm² at the cathode). The reduction of critical raw materials content is reported feasible reducing the catalysts at a nano-scale.

Table 4. State-of-the-art and future targets for Hydrogen production from renewable electricity for energy storage and grid balancing using **high-temperature SOE**

No	Parameter	Unit	State of the art		FCH-JU target		
			2012	2017	2020	2024	2030
Generic system*							
1	Electricity consumption @rated capacity	kWh/kg	n.a.	41	40	39	37
2	Availability	%	n.a.	na	95%	98%	99%
3	Capital cost	€/(kg/d)	n.a.	12 000	4500	2400	1500
4	O&M cost	€/(kg/d)/yr	n.a.	600	225	120	75
Specific system							
5	Reversible efficiency	%	n.a.	50%	54%	57%	60%
6	Reversible capacity	%	n.a.	20%	25%	30%	40%
Stack							
7	Production loss rate	%/1000hrs	n.a.	2,8	1,9	1,2	0,5

Notes:

**Standard boundary conditions that apply to all system KPIs: input of AC power and tap water; output of hydrogen meeting ISO 14687-2 at atmospheric pressure. Correction factors may be applied if actual boundary conditions are different.*

- 3) and 4) similar conditions as for alkaline technology (previous tables);
- 5) Reversible efficiency is defined as the electricity generated in reversible mode of the electrolyser, divided by the lower heating value of hydrogen consumed;
- 6) Reversible capacity is defined as a percentage of the electric capacity in electrolyser mode; Degradation at thermo-neutral conditions in percent loss of production-rate (hydrogen power output) at constant efficiency. Note this is a different definition as for low temperature electrolysis, reflecting the difference in technology.

Table 5. State-of-the-art and future targets for **Hydrogen production with low carbon footprint from other resources**

No	Parameter	Unit	State of the art		FCH-JU target		
			2012	2017	2020	2024	2030
Hydrogen from raw biogas¹							
1	System energy use	kWh/kg	62	56	56	55	53
2	System capital cost	€/(kg/d)	4200	3800	3100	2500	1500
High temp. water splitting¹							
3	System energy use	kWh/kg	120	110	100	94	88
4	System capital cost	€/(kg/d)	4000	3500	2500	1700	1400
5	System lifetime	years	0,5	1	2	10	10
Biological H2 production							
6	System carbon yield	H ₂ /C	0,60	0,62	0,64	0,65	0,65
7	Reactor production rate	kg/m ³ reactor	2	10	40	100	200
8	Reactor scale	m ³	0.05	0.5	1	10	10

Correlating R&D-specific KPIs

In the tables below, quantitative indicators are defined for the required progress in key areas of European FCH technology. These indicators are considered valid references on the pathway to the achievement of the high-level application specific KPIs defined by the FCH JU in Section A.1 above. To this effect the link to, and impact on, the latter KPIs is explained for each of the R&D KPIs, which are subdivided according to horizontal thematic areas.

This section is missing some specific values and should be considered as an open document to be continuously updated by the research community of HYDROGEN EUROPE RESEARCH, research grouping of the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking and the Joint Programme FUEL CELLS AND HYDROGEN of the European Energy Research Alliance.

Table 6. State-of-the-art and future KPIs targets for fuel cell and electrolyser electrolytes

No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology (e.g. PEMFC, SOEC, AEC, etc.)	Applicable conditions (e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	Corresponding FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
1	Through-plane proton areal resistance	mΩcm ²	PEMFC	80°C, 100%RH	10	6	A.1.9 no.1,8
				80°C, 50%RH	50	20	
2	Self-diffusion resistance	x10 ³ s.cm ⁻¹	PEMFC	30°C, 100%RH	300		A.1.9 no.1,8
3	Pervaporation resistance	s.cm ⁻¹	PEMFC	30°C	30		A.1.9 no.1,8
4	Electroosmotic drag coefficient	-	PEMFC	30°C	1 ^d		A.1.9 no.1,8
5	Hydrogen cross-over current	mA.cm ⁻²	PEMFC	80°C, 100%RH, PH ₂ =1 bar	1.1		A.1.9 no.1,7, 8
6	Oxygen cross-over current	mA.cm ⁻²	PEMFC	80°C, 100%RH, PO ₂ =1bar	2.4		A.1.9 no.1,7, 8
7	In-plane swelling	%	PEMFC	From dry to wet in water @ 80°C	10	5	A.1.9 no.4,5, 7
8	Increase of performance through the adoption of innovative binders	%	Low-temperature FC & Electrolyser technologies		Reference	>25%	A.1.8 no.4 ,5 A.1.9 no. 7,8
9	Conductivity	S / cm	PCC	400°C-700°C	10 ⁻³ S / cm		A.1.10 no. 1
10	Cost	€.m ⁻²	PEMFC	-	15		A.1.9 no.2
11	Durability	Cycles until >15 mA.cm ⁻² H ₂ cross-over or >20% loss in OCV	PEMFC	Combined chemical/mechanical	-		A.1.9 no.4,5, 7

Notes:

The evaluation of many of the above technical criteria can be done in-situ or in a real fuel cell. This requires to put the membrane in an MEA. It would be interesting to have criteria which can be obtained ex-situ in order to obtain a relationship between properties and performance/durability, which is still missing. As such, giving values for the targets is hazardous. One good starting point would be to measure all these values on one type of sample, an EU reference sample like for example the membrane used in the MEA of the FCH JU project Autostack Core.

- 1) *Criterion taken from USA DoE (see Introduction). Measurement by impedance spectroscopy of the ohmic resistance due to the membrane (RO_{hm} in Ohm). The value is obtained by multiplying the surface of the membrane (S) and RO_{hm} .*
- 2) *Measured on Gore 820.15 membrane*
- 3) *Measurement by PFG-NMR of the water self-diffusion coefficient D_{H_2O} in $cm^2 \cdot s^{-1}$. Value obtained by dividing thickness of the membrane (e) in cm by D_{H_2O} Kusoglu, A., Weber, A.Z., Chem. Rev. 2017, 117, 987–1104*
- 5) *Criterion taken from USA DoE (see Introduction). Measurement of water flow across membrane when a gradient of RH is imposed on each side: 90%RH on one side and 20%RH.*
- 6) *Criterion taken from USA DoE (see Introduction). Measurement method to be defined*
- 7) *For H₂ test methods, see M. Inaba et. al. Electrochimica Acta, 51, 5746, 2006. For O₂ test methods, see Zhang et. al. Journal of The Electrochemical Society, 160, F616-F622, 2013. (Same methods as referenced by DoE.)*
- 8) *Indication for electrolyte manufacturing processes.*
- 9) *Optimizing the synthesis and manufacturing of highly dense crystalline electrolyte for application in Proton conducting Ceramic Cells*
- 10) *Criterion taken from USA DoE (see Introduction).*
- 11) *Cycle from DoE. Journal of The Electrochemical Society, 165 (6) F3085-F3093 (2018)*

Table 7. State-of-the-art and future targets for fuel cell and electrolyser electrodes and catalysts

No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology (e.g. PEMFC, SOEC, ...)	Applicable conditions (e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	Corresponding FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
1	Area-Specific Resistance	Ωcm^2	All cell technologies	At respective operation temperature	0.25	<0.1	A.1.8 no.1,5 A.1.9 no.1,8 A.1.10 no.1
2	Current density	A/cm^2	Fuel Cell	At respective operation temperature, 50 mV overpotential (FC anode) 100 mV (FC cathode)	0.3	0.8	A1.13 no.6 A1.14 no.6 A1.15 no.6
			Electrolysis	100 mV (cathode) 200 mV (anode)	0.6	>1	A.1.8 no.4 A.1.9 no.7 A.1.10 no.7
3	Catalysts/electrode durability	hours	All cell technologies	Under relevant operation conditions	5000-10000	>40000	A.1.8 no.4, 3 A.1.9 no.7, 3 A.1.10 no.7, 4
4	Precious metal loading	mg/cm^2	PEM fuel cells/electrolyzers	Under relevant operation conditions	0.25	<0.1	A.1.9 no.9
5	Sulfur Tolerance of Anodes	ppm	SOFC	700°C-900°C	0 ppm for Ni-YSZ	10	A.1.13 no.4,5,8
6	Redox cycling ability	No.	SOFC	600-900 C	10	>100	A.1.13 no.4,5,8
7	Carbon Tolerant fuel electrodes for co-electrolysis (ASR)	$\Omega.\text{cm}^2$	SOE	700°C-900°C P =1- 10 bar	>1	0,1	A.1.10 no. 4

Notes:

- 5) Development of materials /Structures/strategies for enhancing sulfur tolerance of SOFCs
- 6) Development of novel electrocatalysts for co-electrolysis and CO₂ reduction

Table 8. State-of-the-art and future targets for fuel cell and electrolyser stack materials and design

No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology (e.g. PEMFC, SOEC, ...)	Applicable conditions (e.g. T , J , #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	Corresponding FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
1	Gas Diffusion Layer (GDL) Thickness	μm	PEMFC		~ 180-400	<50	
2	GDL Area weight	g/m^2	PEMFC		~ 50-200	50	
3	GDL Mean pore diameter	μm	PEMFC		~ 0.8-3 (GDM) ~ 0.01-0.5 (MPL)		
4	GDL Cost	$\text{€}/\text{m}^2$	PEMFC			5	
5	GDL Electrical resistance (in-plane/through-plane) ⁽¹⁾ @1Mpa	$\text{m}\Omega\text{cm}^2$	PEMFC		~ 1-5/ 8-20	~ 0.5/2	
6	GDL Gas permeability (in-plane/through-plane) ⁽¹⁾	m^2	PEMFC		~ 10^{-11} - to 10^{-12} ~ 10^{-12} - to 10^{-14}		
7	GDL Relative gas diffusion coefficient ⁽¹⁾	-	PEMFC		~ 0.1-0.5	~ 0.7	
8	GDL Thermal conductivity ⁽¹⁾	$\text{W}/\text{m}/\text{K}$	PEMFC		~ 0.4-0.7	~ 5	
9	Contact resistance ⁽⁴⁾	$\text{m}\Omega\text{cm}^2$	PEMFC		~ 3-30	~ 0.5-2	
10	GDL Wettability (global and local)	-	PEMFC		Hydrophobic treatments are not stable (chemical/mechanical degradation), mixed wettability with hydrophilic and hydrophobic zones, not controlled distribution of wettability	Control and tune local wettability	
11	Young modulus	MPa	PEMFC		$E_x=E_y\sim 5000-10000$ $E_z\sim 10-100$		
12	Open porosity	%	PEMFC		~ 70-80 (GDM) ~ 40 (MPL)		

No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology (e.g. PEMFC, SOEC, ...)	Applicable conditions (e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	Corresponding FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
13	Interconnect lifetime	hours	PEMFC,PEMEC,AEC			>40 000	A.1.8 no. 3 A.1.9 no. 3 A.1.13 no.2,4 A.1.14 no.2,4 A.1.15 no.2,4
14	Interconnect cost target	€/kW	PEMFC,PEMEC,AEC			<3	A.1.8 no.2 A.1.9 no. 2
15	Electrical conductivity	S/cm	PEMFC,PEMEC,AEC			>100	A.1.8 no.1 A.1.9 no. 1
16	Interconnect lifetime	hours	SOFC, SOEC		40k	>100k	A.1.10 no. 4 A.1.13 no.2,4 A.1.14 no.2,4 A.1.15 no.2,4
17	Interconnect (w/o Cr-barrier layer)cost target	€/kW	SOFC (for SOEC, divide by 3)	Small series	1300-1800	<300	A.1.10 no. 3 A.1.13 no.1 A.1.14 no.1 A.1.15 no.1
18	Cost target Cr-barrier coating	€/kW	SOFC (for SOEC, divide by 3)		1050	30	A.1.10 no. 3 A.1.13 no.1 A.1.14 no.1 A.1.15 no.1
18a	Cost target Cr-barrier coating	€/kW	SOFC (for SOEC, divide by 3)	MCF by APS	1050	120	Idem as 6.
19	ASR of Protective coating for the interconnect at the Fuel Side	mΩ.cm ²	SOE (steam electrolysis)	700°C – 750°C (ASC) 800°C -900°C (ESC) Steady state	-	<10	A.1.10 no. 1, 5
20	ASR of Anti coking protective coatings for the interconnect at the fuel side	mΩ.cm ²	SOE co-electrolysis	700°C – 750°C (ASC) 800°C -900°C (ESC) Steady state	-	<10	A.1.10 no. 1, 5

21	Degradation by cycling (contact losses?)	% V/cycle	SOFC		1	0,05	
No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology (e.g. PEMFC, SOEC, ...)	Applicable conditions (e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	Corresponding FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
21a	Degradation by cycling (contact losses?)	% V/cycle	SOEC		0,3	0,05	
22	SOFC sealing life time	Thermal cycles	SOFC, SOEC	Ambient – 700°C	<100	200-1000 (TBD, 2 different inputs provided)	A.1.10 no. 4 A.1.13 no.2,4 A.1.14 no.2,4 A.1.15 no.2,4
23	Cost of stack sealant	€/kW	SOFC (for SOEC, divide by 3 to 4)	Small series production	500	45	A.1.10 no. 3 A.1.13 no.1 A.1.14 no.1 A.1.15 no.1
24	Cost of electrode contact material	€/kW	SOFC (for SOEC, divide by 3 to 4)	Mesh of Nickel wire	70	5	A.1.10 no. 3 A.1.13 no.1 A.1.14 no.1 A.1.15 no.1
25	ASR of electrode-contact-layer	mOhm/cm ²	SOFC, SOEC	At xxx°C	40	20	
26	Heat-up time of stack from ambient to operating temperature	min	SOFC	Ambient – 700°C	120	30	

Notes:

- 1) This value varies with clamping pressure and so also between rib and channel;
- 2) Uncompressed;
- 3) Large variations depending on the GDL grade, especially with and without MPL. Optimum value could be different depending on operating conditions and position inside the cell (inlet/outlet);
- 4) With stainless steel plate, compressed;
- 6) Optimum value could be different depending on operating conditions and position inside the cell (inlet/outlet);
- 7) Optimum value could be different depending on operating conditions and position inside the cell (inlet/outlet);

- 11) *Optimum value could be different depending on operating conditions and position inside the cell (inlet/outlet);*
- 15) *Depends on the stack design;*
- 23) *Operating temperature should be defined in order for these numbers to have a meaning. Perhaps one should instead define the number in terms of the total stack resistance. I.e. contact layer resistance should equal less than XX % of total resistance of a stack single repeating unit (See 13a);*
- 24) *SoA value taken from Juelich light-weight design.*

Table 9. State-of-the-art and future targets for fuel cell and electrolyser systems

No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology (e.g. PEMFC, SOEC, ...)	Applicable conditions (e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	Corresponding FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
<i>Balance of Plant (BoP) components</i>							
1	Corrosion rate	µA/cm ²	BoP parts in alkaline or acidic media	n.a.		< 0.1	A.1.8-9 no.3 (O&M) A.1.13-15 no.5 (MTBF)
	Oxidation mass gain	mg/1000 hrs	Steel components in HT systems	Operating conditions		< 0.2	A.1.10 no.4 (O&M) A.1.13-15 no.5 (MTBF)
2	Cost of materials	€/kg	All BoP parts	n.a.		< 5	A.1.8-9 no.2 (CAPEX) A.1.10 no.3 (CAPEX) A.1.13-15 no.1 (CAPEX)
3	Cumulative Cr evaporation from BOP parts	kg/m ² for 1000 hrs	Steel components in HT systems	n.a.		< 0.0002	A.1.13-15 no.2 (Lifetime)
4	Coating resistance	hrs	Heat exchangers	n.a.		> 40kh	A.1.13-15 no.5 (MTBF)
5	Coating costs	€/m ²	Coatings and linings for corrosion resistance in alkaline and acidic media in BoP	n.a.		< 700	A.1.8-9 no.2 (CAPEX) A.1.10 no.3 (CAPEX) A.1.13-15 no.1 (CAPEX)
6	Influence of coating on functional properties of the Parts	%	Coatings and linings for corrosion resistance in alkaline and acidic media in BoP	n.a.		< 10	A.1.8 no.1 A.1.9 no.1 A.1.13 no.6,7 A.1.14 no.6, 7 A.1.15 no.6, 7
7	Degradation	%	Catalysts/support for reforming and POX	n.a.		< 10	A.1.13-15 no.2 (Lifetime)
<i>BoP integration</i>							
8	BoP Cost	€/kW	Total system, All FC & electrolyser technologies	n.a.		< 400	A.1.8 no.2 A.1.9 no.2 A.1.10 no.3 A.1.13 no.1 A.1.14 no.1 A.1.15 no.1

9	Footprint reduction	%	Total system, All FC & electrolyser technologies	n.a.		> 15	A.1.9 no.6
10	System efficiency gain	%	Total system, All FC & electrolyser technologies	n.a.		> 3	A.1.8 no.1 A.1.9 no.1 A.1.13 no.6,7 A.1.14 no.6, 7 A.1.15 no.6, 7

Table 10. State-of-the-art and future targets for fuel cell and electrolyser modelling, validation and diagnostics

No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology (e.g. PEMFC, SOEC, ...)	Applicable conditions (e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	Corresponding FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
Diagnostics hardware and software							
1	Detection & Isolation accuracy	%	PEMFC, SOFC	nominal & faulty states	93	97	A.1.1 no. 3 A.1.2 no. 3 A.1.3 no. 3 A.1.4 no. 2 A.1.5 no. 4, 5 A.1.13 no. 3, 5 A.1.14 no. 3, 5 A.1.15 no. 3, 5
2	Fault Detection & Isolation accuracy	%	PEMFC, SOFC	faulty states	95	99	A.1.1 no. 3 A.1.2 no. 3 A.1.3 no. 3 A.1.4 no. 2 A.1.5 no. 4, 5 A.1.13 no. 3, 5 A.1.14 no. 3, 5 A.1.15 no. 3, 5
3	Fault Detection & Isolation precision	%	PEMFC, SOFC	faulty states	95	99	A.1.1 no. 3 A.1.2 no. 3 A.1.3 no. 3 A.1.4 no. 2 A.1.5 no. 4, 5 A.1.13 no. 3, 5 A.1.14 no. 3, 5 A.1.15 no. 3, 5
4	False alarm rate	%	PEMFC, SOFC	nominal states	5	2	A.1.1 no. 3 A.1.2 no. 3 A.1.3 no. 3 A.1.4 no. 2 A.1.5 no. 4, 5 A.1.13 no. 3, 5 A.1.14 no. 3, 5 A.1.15 no. 3, 5

No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology (e.g. PEMFC, SOEC, ...)	Applicable conditions (e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	Corresponding FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
5	Missed fault rate	%	PEMFC, SOFC	faulty states	5	2	A.1.1 no. 3 A.1.2 no. 3 A.1.3 no. 3 A.1.4 no. 2 A.1.5 no. 4, 5 A.1.13 no. 3, 5 A.1.14 no. 3, 5 A.1.15 no. 3, 5
Modelling and validation							
6	Predictability of cell component model based on <i>ab-initio</i> properties calculation and material properties characterization	%	All cell technologies	All conditions	<80	90	A.1.1 no. 1,3 A.1.2 no. 1,3 A.1.3 no. 1,3 A.1.4 no. 1,2,4 A.1.5 no. 4, 5 A.1.8 no. 4,5,6 A.1.9 no. 4,5,6 A.1.10 no. 5,7 A.1.13 no. 3, 5 A.1.14 no. 3, 5 A.1.15 no. 3, 5

Notes:

- 1) Ratio between the correct number of detection & isolation assignments (both nominal & faulty) and the overall number of experienced/tested states;
- 2) Ratio between the correct number of fault detection & isolation assignments and the overall number of experienced/tested faulty states;
- 3) Ratio between the correct number of fault detection & isolation assignments and the overall number of faulty assignments;
- 4) Ratio between the incorrect faulty assignments and the overall number of experienced/tested states;
- 5) Ratio between the non-detected faulty states and the overall number of experienced/tested state;

Table 11. State-of-the-art and future targets for (non-electrolytic) hydrogen production and hydrogen handling

No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology (e.g. PEMFC, SOEC, ...)	Applicable conditions (e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	Corresponding FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
Compression & Liquefaction							
1	Capital cost compressor	€/(kg/day)	Electrochemical compressor		190-1900	500	A.1.7 no. 9 A.1.11 no.2,4
			Thermochemical compressor	120 kg/day. 2.4 pressure ratio.	1083-2550 1835 (24 kg/day) 1041 (2400 kg/day)		
2	Operating cost compression	€/yr	Electrochemical compressor	n.a.		600	A.1.7 no. 7
			Thermochemical compressor	120 kg/day. 2.4 pressure ratio. 2000 h/yr 0.1€/kWh	1240		
3	Compression efficiency	kWh/kg g kWh/kg g kWh/kg g	Electrochemical compressor	0.8-100 MPa	2		A.1.7 no. 3
			Thermochemical compressor	0.8-100 MPa	10-25%. 6-10 kWh/kg		
4	Durability	Hours	Electrochemical compressor	n.a.	10 years	20 years	A.1.7 no.2,4,5,6
			Thermochemical compressor	n.a.			

5	Liquefaction efficiency	process	kWh/kg	Liquid Hydrogen	0.1MPa, 25K	12.5-15		A.1.12 no.3
Purification								
6				PSA				
No.	Parameter		Unit	Applicable technology (e.g. PEMFC, SOEC, ...)	Applicable conditions (e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	Corresponding FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
	Capital Cost purificationsystem		€/(Kg/day)	(Pressure adsorption) swing	500 kg/day	1800 €/(kg/day)	450 €/(kg/day)	A.1.7 no. 9 A.1.11 no.2,4
				TSA (Temperature Adsorption) Swing				
				Membrane				
7	Operative cost purificationsystem		€/yr	(Pressure adsorption) swing	500kg/day	333 000 – 1 232 000 €/yr	249 750€/yr	A.1.7 no. 7
				TSA (Temperature Adsorption) Swing				
				Membrane				
8	Purification efficiency		%	(Pressure adsorption) swing	500kg/day	90	95	A.1.7 no. 3
				TSA (Temperature Swing Adsorption)		95	98	
				Membrane				
9	Hydrogen selectivity		1	Membrane separator	25 kg/day			A.1.11 no.1,6,7 A.1.12 no.3
Non-electrolytic hydrogen production								
10	Stable, autonomous operation of biomass gasficiation process		hours	Biomass and waste gasification	n.a.	10 000	88 000	n.a.

11	Automatic adaption of operating conditions to feedstock quality in Gasification	%	Biomass and waste gasification	n.a.	0	100	n/a
12	Production of homogeneous biomass feedstock for Gasification	n.a.	Biomass and waste gasification	n.a.	n.a.	quality margin +/-5%	n/a
No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology (e.g. PEMFC, SOEC, ...)	Applicable conditions(e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	Corresponding FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
13	Tar content after cracking/clean-up	mg/Nm ₃	Biomass and waste gasification	n.a.	<500	<1	n.a.
14	Purity of hydrogen produced	%	Algae	n.a.	66	99.9	A.1.11
15	Quantum yield	%	Photocatalytic reforming of biomass derivatives (ethanol, glycerol, glucose)	Catalyst: PGM-free on titania Light: UV-A	25-30	35	n.a.
				Catalyst: PGM on titania Light: UV-A	50-70	80	
16	Yield referred to photocatalyst activity (per gram of catalyst)	mmol H ₂ /g.h	Photocatalytic reforming of alcohols (ethanol, glycerol)	Catalyst: PGM-free on titania Light: UV-A	10-15	>150	n.a.
				Catalyst: PGM on titania Light: UV-A	30-40	>500	
17a	Efficiency of Hydrogen production	%	Algae	n.a.	2 to 3	5	A.1.11 no.1,2
			Photocatalytic water splitting	n.a.	5	>10	can apply to A.1.11
Transport							
18	Transport size trail	Kg	Compressed gas storage	n.a.			n.a.
			Liquid storage	n.a.	5000	4000	n.a.

Notes:

1) Capital cost of compression for kg of compressed Hydrogen. References:

- SOA 2020, thermochemical compressor (24 kg/day): Stamatakis, E., Zoulias, E., Tzamalis, G., Massina, Z., Analytis, V., Christodoulou, C., & Stubos, A. (2018). Metal hydride hydrogen compressors: Current developments & early markets. *Renewable Energy*, 127, 850–862. doi:10.1016/j.renene.2018.04.073;

- SOA 2020, thermochemical compressor (24 kg/day): DASILVA, E. (1993). *Industrial prototype of a hydrogen compressor based on metallic hydride technology. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 18(4), 307–311;
 - SOA 2020, thermochemical compressor (240 kg/day): Stamatakis E. *Benchmark Analysis & Pre-feasibility study for the market penetration of Metal Hydride Hydrogen Compressor. Integrated, Innovative Renewable Energy – Hydrogen Systems and Applications Workshop. July, 2017, 5-7. Athens, Greece;*
- The value of the maintenance costs has been estimated with the following calculation $(0.06 \cdot (120/24) \cdot 2000 = 600 \text{ €/yr})$ by considering operational costs of 0.06 €/kg
- 2) Operative cost of compression for kg of compressed hydrogen;
 - 3) Efficiency of compression expressed as kWh for any kg of compressed H₂;
 - 4) Durability of compressor in constant operation;
 - 5) Efficiency of liquefaction process. Amount of energy spent to liquefy 1 kg of hydrogen. Reference:
 - SOA 2020, liquefaction processes: Moradi, R., & Groth, K. M. (2019). *Hydrogen storage and delivery: Review of the state of the art technologies and risk and reliability analysis. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*;
 - 6) Capital cost of purification system for 500 kg/day hydrogen production system;
 - 7) Operating cost of purification system for 500 kg/day hydrogen production system;
The value has been estimated considering 8000 hours of operation per year and operating costs between 2.0 and 7.4 €/kg for the SoA and 1.5 €/kg by 2030.
 - 8) Efficiency of purification. Percentage of wasted hydrogen with respect to hydrogen inlet mass flow rate;
 - 9) Membrane selectivity is the ratio of hydrogen diffusion flow and overall diffusion flow through it. Hydrogen purity must be compliance to ISO 14687 and ISO/TS 19883. Protocol test to be described;
 - 13) State of art 2020 from BLAZE project (H2020 Grant Agreement 815284, 2019);
 - 14) Efficiency of hydrogen production as kWh spent for any kg of produced H₂ for the different technologies reported (considering steam production, heat demand);
 - 15) Hydrogen yield per absorbed photon. References:
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 - 18) Maximum amount of hydrogen transporting by trail. The estimation for the liquid storage expected by 2030 is considered for LH₂ tank trailer payload

Table 12. State-of-the-art and future targets for hydrogen storage

No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology	Applicable conditions (e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
1.	Gravimetric density	wt.% i.e. 100*kg H2/kg system (material)	Compressed gas	15 °C, 35 MPa	7	7.5	A.1.6 no.1-3, A.1.12 no.1,2
				15 °C, 70 MPa	5.7	7.5	A.1.6 no1-3 A.1.12 no.1,2
			Carriers by physisorption	77 K, 5.6 MPa	(10)	15	n.a.
			Carriers by chemisorption (e.g. metal/complex hydrides)	LT (RT-100°C), 1MPa	1-2	3.5	A.1.6 no. 3
				MT (100-300°C), 1MPa	2.5 - 5	5-8	A.1.6.3: 6
			Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier	HT (>300°C), 1MPa	(7.1)	10	A.1.6 no. 3
2.	Volumetric density	g H2/liter system (material)	Compressed gas	15 °C, 35 MPa	30.8	40	can apply to A.1.3, A.1.6
				15 °C, 70 MPa	23 - 42	70	can apply to A.1.3, A.1.6
			Carriers by physisorption	15°C, 70 MPa	58	80	n.a.
				77 K, 5.6 MPa	40	60	n.a.
			Carriers by chemisorption (e.g. metal/complex hydrides)	LT (RT-100°C), 1MPa	(90)	120	A.1.6 no. 2
				MT (100-300°C), 1MPa	10 (50)	80	n.a.
			Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier	HT (>300°C), 1MPa	50 (130)	150	n.a.
				50-300 °C, 0.1 MPa	(50 -100) (56)	+20%	n.a.
			Liquid Hydrogen	0.1 MPa, 20.25 K	40	+20%	n.a.
			No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology	Applicable conditions (e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)

					70		
3.	Scalability	kg H2	Carriers by physisorption	77 K, 5.6 MPa	>1	>1	n.a.
			Carriers by chemisorption (e.g. metal/complex hydrides)	LT (RT-100°C), 1MPa	5-10, 24	5000	n.a.
				MT (100-300°C), 1MPa	1	10	n.a.
				HT (>300°C), 1MPa	150	500	n.a.
			Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier	50-300 °C, 0.1 MPa	>5000		can apply to A.1.4
4.	Release energyuse Heat exchange	kWh/kg H2	Carriers by physisorption	77 K, 5.6 MPa			n.a.
			Carriers by chemisorption (e.g. metal/complex hydrides)	LT (RT-100°C), 1MPa	3.5	1	n.a.
				MT (100-300°C), 1MPa	3-10	1	n.a.
				HT (>300°C), 1MPa	10	3	n.a.
			Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier	50-300 °C, 0.1 MPa	9 – 10	5	n.a.
			Liquid Hydrogen	0.1 MPa, 20.25 K			n.a.
5.	Boiling Off	kW/kg	Liquid hydrogen	0.1 MPa, 20.25 K	0.3-3.0	0.1	n.a.
6.	Degradation	wt. %/cycle	Compressed gas	15 °C, 35 MPa			n.a.
				15 °C, 700 bar			n.a.
			Carriers by physisorption	15 °C, 70 MPa			n.a.
No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology	Applicable conditions (e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
				77 K, 5.6 MPa			n.a.
				LT (RT-100°C), 1MPa			n.a.
				MT (100-300°C), 1MPa			n.a.

			Carriers by chemisorption (e.g. metal/complex hydrides)	HT (>300°C), 1MPa			n.a.
			Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier	50-300 °C, 0.1 MPa	0.1	0.08	n.a.
7.	Gas permeability	NL/m ² /day	Compressed gas	15°C, 35 MPa		0.05	n.a.
				15 °C, 70 MPa			n.a.
8.	Tensile strength	GPa	Compressed gas	15°C, 35 MPa			n.a.
				15 °C, 70 MPa			n.a.
			Carriers by chemisorption (e.g. metal/complex hydrides)	1 MPa	1.0		n.a.
9.	Storage system Cost	€/kg H ₂	Compressed gas	15 °C, 35 MPa			n.a.
				15 °C, 70 MPa	1500	300	A.1.6 no. 1 A.1.12 no.2
			Liquid Hydrogen	0.1 MPa, 20.25 K			A.1.12 no.5
			Carriers by physisorption	77 K, 5.6 MPa	?	300	n.a.
			Carriers by chemisorption (e.g. metal/complex hydrides)	LT (RT-100°C),1MPa	3000	300	n.a.
				MT (100-300°C),1MPa	5000	300	n.a.
				HT (>300°C), 1MPa			n.a.
			Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier	50-300 °C, 0.1 MPa			n.a.
No.	Parameter	Unit	Applicable technology	Applicable conditions (e.g. T, J, #cycles, ...)	SoA 2020	Target 2030	FCH JU MAWP KPIs (e.g. A.1.1 no.1)
	Kinetics		Carriers by physisorption	77 K, 5.6 MPa			n.a.
				LT (RT-100°C),1MPa	10	5	n.a.
					MT (100-300°C),1MPa	10	5

10.	sorption	%/min	Carriers by chemisorption (e.g. metal/complex hydrides)	HT (>300°C), 1MPa			n.a.
11.	Cyclability	N°	Carriers by physisorption	77 K, 5.6 MPa			n.a.
			Carriers by chemisorption (e.g. metal/complex hydrides)	LT (RT-100°C), 1MPa		10 000	n.a.
				MT (100-300°C), 1MPa		2000	n.a.
			HT (>300°C), 1MPa		2000	n.a.	
Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier	50-300 °C, 0.1 MPa				n.a.		

Notes:

- 1) Gravimetric density of only storage tank or only sorbed material as. Kg of stored H₂ with respect to the weight of storage system. For reversible metal hydride, three temperature categories are included: low temperature (LT), mid temperature (MD) and high temperature (HT).

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- 2) Volumetric density of only storage tank or sorbed material as. g of stored H₂ with respect to the volume of storage system. For reversible metal hydride, three temperature categories are included: low temperature (LT), mid temperature (MD) and high temperature (HT). This KPI is quite difficult to standardize, due to different value obtained by the same tank but with different dimensions.

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